

Cite this: *Food Funct.*, 2021, **12**, 3280

Correction: Suppressive effects of *Streptococcus thermophilus* KLDS 3.1003 on some foodborne pathogens revealed through *in vitro*, *in vivo* and genomic insights

Smith Etareri Evivie,^{a,b,c} Matthew Chidozie Ogwu,^{d,e} Amro Abdelazez,^{f,g} Xin Bian,^h Fei Liu,^a Bailiang Li^{*a} and Guicheng Huo^{*a}

DOI: 10.1039/d1fo90021h
rsc.li/food-function

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The authors regret that the corresponding authors were incorrectly shown in the original article. The corrected author list and corresponding authors are as shown above.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

^aKey Laboratory of Dairy Science, Ministry of Education, College of Food Science, Northeast Agricultural University, Harbin 150030, China.

E-mail: besta_intercom@yahoo.com, liufei@neau.edu.cn, 15846092362@163.com, gchuo@neau.edu.cn; Tel: +86-451-55191807; Fax: +86-451-55190577

^bDepartment of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Benin, Benin City 300001, Nigeria. E-mail: besta_intercom@yahoo.com

^cDepartment of Food Science and Human Nutrition, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Benin, Benin City 300001, Nigeria. E-mail: besta_intercom@yahoo.com

^dSchool of Biosciences and Veterinary Medicine, University of Camerino 60232, Camerino Marche – Floristic Research Centre of the Apennine Gran Sasso and Monti della Laga National Park, San Colombo, 67021 Barisciano, L'Aquila, Italy. E-mail: matthew.ogwu@uniben.edu

^eDepartment of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Science, University of Benin, Benin City 300001, Nigeria. E-mail: matthew.ogwu@uniben.edu

^fDepartment of Dairy Microbiology, Animal Production Research Institute, Agricultural Research Centre, Dokki, Giza 12618, Egypt. E-mail: 3082787118@qq.com

^gInstitute of Microbe and Host Health, Linyi University, Linyi 276005, China. E-mail: 3082787118@qq.com

^hDepartment of Food Engineering, Harbin Commerce University, Harbin 150028, China. E-mail: bianbian1225@163.com

